

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

URBAN AND URBAN PLANNING AS AN OBJECT OF PHILOSOPHICAL AND AESTHETIC RESEARCH

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Abstract: *The article talks about the philosophical and aesthetic issues of the city and urban planning, generalizes empirical experience.*

Keywords: *urban planning, aesthetics, urban aesthetics, construction, infrastructure, housing, complex, transport, urban planning*

The terms "urban culture", "urban urbanization", and "urban aesthetics" are commonly used in the field of building architecture. True, the concept of "urban culture" is used in philosophical and aesthetic sciences, especially in the field of cultural studies. Emphasis is placed on the lifestyle and cultural life of the city's residents. [1; 2; 3]. Because these approaches assume that urban culture and urbanization, the way of life of the urban population differs from the traditional way of life in the agro environment. However, the city, as a separate social space of the population agglomeration, is a cultural aesthetic entity with its own social characteristics. The concepts of "City" and "Urban Planning" can be understood through their philosophical and aesthetic interpretations.

The etymological interpretation of the concept of "city" is often derived from the agglomeration of the population, lifestyle, differentiation in the division of labor, the construction of more intellectual labor, the widespread development of infrastructure, high urbanization. [4; 5]. However, these interpretations are social markers of urban culture and lifestyle. In general, the etymological interpretation of the word "city" is almost non-existent in the scientific literature. According to Wikipedia, the city is a relatively large and permanent region. For many cities, local law gives them a special administrative, legal, or historical status. For example, the city of Tashkent in Uzbekistan has a special place in the region and the regional center. In Europe, it has historically been considered a city in any settlement with

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its own saber. According to the above source, which is a city with a mosque in the east, including Central Asia and Muslim countries, according to ancient historical traditions, "Cities" usually have a complex sanitary, road and street, housing and transport system. will be. Cities with a population of over one million are called megacities; When a city grows and reaches other cities and incorporates them, it becomes a megalopolis. It turns out that the city is home to a large population, mainly engaged in industry, trade, as well as services, management, science and culture. The city is a center for the non-agricultural population. The center should be officially recognized as a city. There are different requirements for this. They are defined by national legislation, ethno-traditions, architecture and demography. However, there is no general standard for determining cities by population. For example, in the Netherlands, Denmark, Spain, a city with a population of 200 people is also a city.

The city has a population of 5,000 in Turkmenistan, 10,000 in Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan, 5,000 to 12,000 in Russia, and 25,000 in Japan. Today, the emergence of new cities in Uzbekistan, with 120 cities and 113 towns, is a natural process, largely due to population growth, the transformation of cities into centers of production, culture and urbanization. Uzbekistan's population is growing by more than half a million every year, and this reproductive growth is creating new cities. The above interpretations cannot be denied, but it is not difficult to see that the emphasis is on geography and agglomeration, while in cultural studies the emphasis is on lifestyle. Some literature also mentions the city's infrastructure management system. [6]. So, according to the existing interpretations, the city is a social space built by the agglomerations for the professional differentiation of different types of labor and a specific way of life. In this space:

1. The population is densely populated;
2. Accumulated communication is intensive;
3. Labor is widely differentiated;
4. Infrastructure is developed;
5. Centralized coordination management is established;
6. Types of educational and household services are organized;
7. There are conveniences of life;
8. Utilities are developed;
9. Life is dynamic;
10. The population is mobile, active;
11. A unique cultural environment will be formed;

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Urbanization is a fun aspect of urban life that attracts rural people. [7; 8]. This means that the concept of a city is difficult to define, because it includes not only geographical space, space, infrastructure, but also a complex of population, migration, division of labor, management, culture and science, recreation, transport and utilities. Urban planning is an area aimed at the formation of this complex, which allows to meet the needs of active living and working, recreation and aesthetics by designing favorable conditions for the population. Urban planning is first and foremost about design, that is, the creation of important infrastructure for urban population, agglomeration and urbanization [9; p.8]. According to experts, urban planning was formed in the twentieth century and includes:

1. Territorial design (population location, master plan, formation of urban infrastructure);
2. Land structure and use;
3. Development of a project proposal in accordance with the territorial division;
4. Design of architectural construction [9 p .; 8];

From this point of view, urban planning is included in the field of architecture and construction. At the same time, urban planning is a special art or creative creativity, a technology for constant research, the creation of new spaces and amenities. [10 c; 10; -12]

The emergence and genesis of cities as socio-economic and cultural spaces provides interesting information. For example, experts say that in the history of the city, which had many names like Bukhara in ancient times, it is almost unheard of. He was known by various names such as Numijkat, Bumichkat, Madanat, At- tujor, Foxira.

The Ark Fortress in Bukhara was founded 1,500 years ago and was inhabited by courtiers. [15]. This means that we have a tradition of urban planning 1.5-2 thousand years ago. According to the Avesto, this tradition dates back at least 3,000 years. It is not enough to interpret urban planning as just an architectural-construction field. Today's urbanization and cultural and social development encourage a philosophical and aesthetic look around. People are interested not only in the new cities, massifs, streets and buildings being built, but also in their philosophical and aesthetic essence, taste-forming appearance, beautiful and compact, clean and vibrant, unique and attractive. In this sense, urban planning is an art, a form of aesthetic creation that shapes the artistic and aesthetic taste of people. Urban planning reflects the fundamental social needs of the population. Socio-economic development and meeting the housing needs of the population are

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at the forefront. Socio-economic development determines the most important aspect of the city, its brand and image. According to senior experts, a person's satisfaction with his social life and the formation of social unity in relationships with other subjects depends on the urban environment, aesthetics [16 c; 21]. Every building and system in the city evokes an aesthetic attitude, even a short shop, a bakery, a small tea shop, which does not attract much attention. Affects a person's emotional and aesthetic perceptions and experiences. [17c; 44; 56; 87]. But sometimes the socio-economic factor outweighs the aesthetic demand. For example, there is a large complex of chemical machinery in Chirchik. The steam turbine from its main shop is also surrounded by barbed wire, and the walls do not meet aesthetic requirements. We can bring such buildings and complexes of socio-economic significance from each of our major cities. The problem is that we cannot ignore such constructions and instantly turn them into an aesthetically pleasing building or complex. Therefore, we can only temporarily adapt their external features to our aesthetic taste. This, in turn, requires the design of future socio-economic institutions, buildings and the surrounding environment in accordance with philosophical and aesthetic requirements. Socio-economic complexes are the arteries of the city, they form new agglomerations and settlements around the city. These complexes can be responsible for the provision of the entire region, but also the regional and national economy with the necessary products, goods and services. Therefore, urban planning in the design of such complexes should be based on socio-economic, as well as philosophical and aesthetic requirements. Housing has become a global problem. The World Bank estimates that by 2030, 3 billion people, or 46% to 47% of the world's population, will be in need of new housing and utilities.

Currently, 23% of the world's population does not own a home, and homelessness has become commonplace in large cities. This is one of the most pressing issues in the Republic of Uzbekistan. President Sh. Mirziyoyev came to power, his decisions were aimed at providing the population with new housing. His program of affordable housing in rural areas for 2017-2021 on the updated model projects "(October 21, 2016)" and "Affordable multi-storey apartment houses in cities in 2017-2021" As a result, in 2016, 13 thousand houses in rural areas, in 2017 - 20.3 thousand in rural areas, in urban areas - 8.5 thousand in total for 2 years. 45,000 houses were built. They spent 6.2 trillion soums. By 2021, 140,000 new homes have been built.

Mortgages play an important role in solving the housing problem. In 2021 alone, mortgage lending banks will allocate 2.4 trillion soums to subsidize interest

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on loans to pay the down payment on mortgage loans to 27,000 or 2.5 times more families than in 2020. We can also cite many such examples [where] the number of mortgage agreements has almost doubled from 121.7 thousand to 238.4 thousand. As a result of these measures, we are witnessing a change in the appearance of our cities. indicates. These innovative researches focus on shaping the image of cities in an aesthetically beautiful, unique way that meets the interests of the population. However, we need to think about how to create a unique aesthetic image of each city, each district, each rural area in a way that combines our unique historical construction experiences and modern approaches.

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